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Equivalence Between the Co-Rotational Finite Element Method and the Absolute Coordinate Formulation in Multibody Dynamics

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ABSTRACT

Geometric nonlinearity arises in problems involving large displacements and rotations, where traditional linear assumptions fail. In the finite element community, several formulations have been developed to address these complexities; the corotational finite element formulation (CRF) has proven to be an efficient alternative to generic total Lagrangian (TL) and updated Lagrangian (UL) approaches for small-strain problems. In the multibody dynamics community, the floating frame of reference formulation (FFRF) is commonly used, employing a gross-motion-following local reference frame per body (also referred to as co-rotational or floating frame), in contrast to CRF's element-based approach. A less known but fully equivalent multibody formulation to FFRF is the absolute coordinate formulation (ACF), which uses absolute coordinates in contrast to rigid body coordinates plus local deformation as in FFRF. This paper demonstrates the equivalence of ACF and CRF, with the only difference being the number of reference frames—body-based versus element-based. Moreover, since CRF, while efficient, faces challenges in real-world multibody simulations due to the computational burden of assigning a reference frame to each finite element, this paper also discusses how CR/ACF can be applied when partitioning bodies into substructures, each equipped with its own reference frame.

1 | Introduction

Geometric nonlinearity arises in problems involving large displacements and rotations, where traditional linear assumptions no longer hold [1, p. 2]. To address such complexities, several finite element formulations have been developed.

Abbreviations: acf, absolute coordinate formulation; ancf, absolute nodal coordinate formulation; cr, corotational; crf, corotational finite element formulation; eicr, element-independent corotational; ffrf, floating frame of reference formulation; tl, total Lagrangian; ul, updated Lagrangian.

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The Total Lagrangian (TL) formulation incorporates all kinematic nonlinear effects, including those arising from large displacements, rotations, and strains, using the undeformed configuration Ω_0 as a reference [2, p. 523]. Similarly, the Updated Lagrangian (UL) formulation accounts for these nonlinearities but references all variables to the last computed configuration [2, p. 523].

Corotational (CR) finite element formulations facilitate the treatment of geometric nonlinearities, provided the small deformation assumption holds within each element [3, tab. 1, p. 555]. The core idea behind co-rotational formulations is the decomposition of motion into two parts: large gross/reference motion and small local deformation. Two key distinctions can be identified within this framework:

- Element- or body-based local reference frames that either follow the gross motion of individual elements or the entire body.
- Rigid body plus local deformation versus absolute nodal coordinates. In the former approach—commonly used in the multibody community in conjunction with the body-based local reference frame in the FFRF—the gross motion of the co-rotational frame itself is directly included in the computational coordinates. The deformation then represents the motion relative to this reference frame. Both the reference motion and the deformation are only defined once the location and orientation of the reference frame have been specified—a process known as imposing reference conditions [4–12]. Depending on the choice of these conditions, the floating frame is not necessarily rigidly attached to a material point. In contrast, the latter approach extracts the frame's motion from absolute nodal coordinates, which capture both gross motion and deformation simultaneously.

The extraction of rigid body motion from global nodal displacements can be achieved through various ways of constructing a local reference frame. Three widely used approaches are identified in [13–15]:

- Side-alignment: In this approach, the local reference frame in 3D is constructed from three vectors defined by the global coordinates of algorithmically selected nodes and orthonormalized using the Gram–Schmidt process. This method is straightforward but sensitive to the node numbering; a change in node order may alter the orientation of the local coordinate system.
- Zero local spin at the element centroid: This method determines the rotation matrix by performing a polar decomposition of the deformation gradient computed at the element centroid. It is independent of node numbering and allows the origin of the local reference frame to be chosen arbitrarily.
- Least-squares minimization: Here, the rigid-body rotation is extracted by minimizing the local nodal displacements, often using a quaternion parametrization of rotations. This method is also independent of node numbering and, from a mathematical standpoint, requires the reference frame's origin to be located at the element centroid.

Exemplary applications of these methods in the context of element-independent corotational (EICR) 3D continuum finite elements can be found in the literature: side-alignment in [16], zero spin in [17], and least-squares minimization in [18]. In the context of ACF, the rigid body translation was computed as the average of the global displacement field, while the rigid body rotation from the average gradient of the global displacement field [19], or alternatively determined also from the positions of three non-colinear points [20]. However, the influence of the specific method used for extracting the rigid body motion has not been studied extensively in the ACF literature.

Approaches that utilize element-based local frames with absolute nodal coordinates are widely known as corotational finite element formulations and are commonly applied in nonlinear structural dynamics. The foundations of the corotational technique in the finite element method were established by Wempner [21] and Belytschko [22, 23] in the late 1960s and 1970s. Building on this work, Rankin et al. [24–26] introduced the pioneering EICR procedure, which soon became a widely adopted standard. The EICR formulation, comprehensively explained in [27], employs a projector matrix that ensures the element internal forces satisfy equilibrium. Subsequent advancements of the EICR approach for 3D continuum elements are reported in [14, 16–18, 28–31].

Despite its benefits—such as the reuse of small-strain elements, potentially including those with material nonlinearity, and the possibility of reduced computational costs compared to universally nonlinear TL or UL formulations [27]—CRF presents challenges in multibody simulations characterized by multiple interconnected components undergoing overall

gross motion over extended time periods. Specifically, assigning a corotational frame to every finite element imposes a computational burden that often becomes prohibitive in large-scale problems.

In contrast, the FFRF utilizes a body-level local frame with separate coordinates for reference motion and local deformations. This approach is particularly suited for analyzing linearly elastic flexible multibody systems, where the small deformation assumption applies at the body level. The FFRF has become the standard method for modeling such systems and is widely recognized as the most commonly used technique, implemented in the majority of commercial software packages [32]. The primary reason for its popularity is its ability to incorporate well-established component mode synthesis techniques. In this approach, flexible deformations are approximated as a linear combination of a small number of component modes, significantly enhancing computational efficiency.

It is also possible to use absolute coordinates as generalized coordinates while employing a single local frame per body, a formulation commonly referred to as ACF in the multibody community. Notably, it can be demonstrated that this formulation is equivalent to the FFRF [32, 33]. However, the ACF approach is not widely recognized, particularly in the finite element community. This lack of awareness is exemplified by the recent work of [34], who proposed a component-level co-rotational approach, wherein an entire body or a substructure (i.e., a part of the body) is assigned a local reference frame, yet no reference is made to ACF. Hence, the primary objective of this paper is to establish that ACF and CRF are fundamentally equivalent, differing only in the number of local reference frames used—specifically, element-based versus body-based frames.

The concept of substructuring in multibody dynamics has a long-standing tradition. When a flexible body undergoes large overall motion (without significant centrifugal forces) and experiences only small deformations, a single floating frame per body can effectively describe its motion, as seen in [35, 36]. However, when the body experiences large deformations or high-speed rotations, a single frame is insufficient, as geometric nonlinear effects significantly influence the stiffness. In such cases, multiple frames per body are required. To address this, [37] proposed partitioning an elastic body into multiple substructures to capture these nonlinear effects, which they applied to beam and truss structures. In their method, the FFRF with modal reduction per substructure was employed, and non-linear algebraic kinematic constraints were imposed to connect the substructures using Lagrange multipliers. Later, similar approaches were developed for modeling wind turbine blades [38–40]. However, Lagrange multipliers increase the number of unknowns, and due to their infinite stiffness, only implicit time integration can be used [39].

To avoid the negative effects of Lagrange multipliers in connecting flexible body substructures, the FFRF with absolute interface coordinates was developed [41–47]. In this approach, substructures (often referred to as superelements or bodies) are constructed using component mode synthesis, based on a 3D solid finite element mesh of a complex-shaped body or substructure. The assembly of substructures is facilitated by sharing the absolute nodal coordinates at the interface, transformed to describe the substructure's configuration relative to an inertial reference frame. Boer et al. [41, 42] introduced a two-node superelement for modeling slender, complex-shaped flexible links characterized by two interface surfaces. More recently, Dwarshuis et al. [46] developed the generalized-strain multimode superelement and extended it by considering deformable interfaces [47]. This enhanced superelement is suitable for modeling applications such as flexure joints, where beam elements model the flexures, and the generalized-strain multimode superelement represents the frame components and critical components.

Several other modifications to FFRF have been proposed to solve geometrically nonlinear problems by partitioning an elastic body into substructures, avoiding the use of Lagrange multipliers for connection. Hodges et al. [48] introduced a hierarchical (parent-child) substructure technique, where the position, orientation, and motion of the child's reference frame are expressed relative to its parent substructure frame. Substructures can be connected through various constraints, including those that eliminate degrees of freedom. Liu and Liew [49] proposed a substructure synthesis method for reducing geometrically nonlinear beam structures by transforming from nodal coordinates to modal coordinates, with substructures connected by sharing modal coordinates at the interface. Zhang et al. [50] developed a substructuring technique using the transfer matrix method to connect substructures of a straight beam undergoing large deformations. Sonnevile et al. [51] presented a general approach for modal reduction of geometrically nonlinear structures within the motion formalism framework. Their formulation requires only a small number of substructures (referred to as modal elements) to accurately capture the nonlinear behavior of a flexible body, with substructures connected by sharing absolute interface coordinates, which are part of each substructure's reduced variable set. Gérardin and Rixen [52] proposed a mixed

FIGURE 1 | Illustration of the substructure partitioning for a finite element discretized body. The orange lines represent the partition boundaries. The substructure fixed frames ${}^{(s)}\bar{\mathcal{F}}$ are translated and rotated relative to the global frame \mathcal{F} .

approach to treat elastic displacement and velocity fields as independent. They avoided Lagrange multipliers for assembling body substructures by transforming local elastic displacements and rotations into global positions and rotations at the boundary nodes, although this increased system complexity and nonlinearity.

The literature on corotational finite element formulations for substructuring seems to be relatively sparse indeed. In [34] spherical joints were used to connect substructures, enforced by Lagrange multipliers. However, such multipliers are not necessary when employing CRF or ACF, as these approaches utilize absolute coordinates, allowing direct assembly of substructures.

By employing a single local frame per body, the stiffness matrix for the entire body can be preassembled, avoiding the need for assembly during iterations. This not only streamlines calculations but also enables similar savings for substructures, where the stiffness matrices can be preassembled once and for all. Therefore, the second objective of this paper is to discuss that CRF/ACF can be applied when partitioning the finite element-discretized body into multiple substructures, each equipped with its own reference frame, as shown in Figure 1. The number of elements within each substructure can be chosen arbitrarily, as long as the small-strain assumption holds within its respective reference frame. Since absolute nodal coordinates are used as generalized coordinates, the substructures can be easily assembled in the standard finite element manner. This approach bridges the gap between ACF and CRF.

Additionally, it is known from ACF that the Jacobian can be efficiently approximated [19], and this concept can be extended to CRF/ACF substructuring. Moreover, each substructure can be reduced using generalized component mode synthesis (GCMS), which represent the standard component mode synthesis modes in any corotated configuration [53, 54].

2 | Terms of Comparison

Since it is essential to clearly define the terms of comparison, we wish to clarify that the formal proof of equivalence is based on displacement-based finite elements, where nodal degrees of freedom are restricted solely to displacements. Specifically, using ABAQUS (Dassault Systèmes) terminology, we consider element such as:

- 2D truss elements: T2D2, T2D3
- 3D truss elements: T3D2, T3D3
- 2D continuum elements: Triangular (CPS3), Quadrilateral (CPS4, CPS8)
- 3D continuum elements: Tetrahedral (C3D4, C3D10), Hexahedral (C3D8, C3D20), Wedge (C3D6)

For the considered elements, the quantities used in the derivations and discussions are defined consistently throughout this paper. Structural finite elements with rotational degrees of freedom, such as beams and shells, are therefore not considered.

3 | Virtual Work Principle for a Deformable Body

In continuum mechanics, the configuration of a body Ω is characterized by the spatial arrangement of all its material points. This configuration is fully described by the continuous displacement field

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}(\chi_0, t), \quad (1)$$

which gives the displacement of each material point from its reference position χ_0 at time t .

The law of motion governing the body's behavior can be expressed via the principle of virtual work. It states that, for any admissible virtual displacement $\delta \mathbf{u}$ the sum of the virtual work δW contributions from inertia, internal stresses Σ , and external forces (body forces \mathbf{b} and surface tractions \mathbf{t}_0) must balance. When referred to the reference configuration Ω_0 , this can be expressed as

$$\delta W = \int_{\Omega_0} \delta \mathbf{u}^\top \ddot{\mathbf{u}} \rho_0 dv_0 + \int_{\Omega_0} \delta \mathbf{E} : \Sigma dv_0 - \int_{\Omega_0} \delta \mathbf{u}^\top \mathbf{b} \rho_0 dv_0 - \int_{\Gamma_0} \delta \mathbf{u}^\top \mathbf{t}_0 da_0 = 0, \quad (2)$$

with density ρ_0 , infinitesimal volume dv_0 and surface da_0 elements, as well as the Green-Lagrange strain tensor \mathbf{E} .

To apply the finite element method, we introduce an interpolation ansatz for the displacement field, that is,

$$\mathbf{u}(\chi_0, t) = \mathbf{S}(\chi_0) \mathbf{c}(t), \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{S} is the shape function matrix, and \mathbf{c} are the finite element nodal displacements. Consequently, the virtual displacements are given as

$$\delta \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{S} \delta \mathbf{c}. \quad (4)$$

Substituting Equations (3) to (4) into the virtual work Equation (2), we obtain the following form

$$\delta \mathbf{c}^\top \mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{c}} + \int_{\Omega_0} \delta \mathbf{E} : \Sigma dv_0 = \delta \mathbf{c}^\top \mathbf{f}, \quad (5)$$

where the mass matrix \mathbf{M} and the external force vector \mathbf{f} are given by

$$\mathbf{M} = \int_{\Omega_0} \mathbf{S}^\top \mathbf{S} \rho_0 dv_0, \quad (6)$$

and

$$\mathbf{f} = \int_{\Omega_0} \mathbf{S}^\top \mathbf{b} \rho_0 dv_0 + \int_{\Gamma_0} \mathbf{S}^\top \mathbf{t}_0 da_0. \quad (7)$$

The internal virtual work associated with the elastic forces needs more attention; it involves the Green-Lagrange strain tensor \mathbf{E} , defined as

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{F}^\top \mathbf{F} - \mathbf{I}), \quad (8)$$

with the deformation gradient

$$\mathbf{F} = \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial \chi_0} \quad (9)$$

$$= \nabla \chi \quad (10)$$

of the current continuous position χ . As mentioned in the introduction, the co-rotational approach is based on the separation of the overall motion into gross motion—described by the translation vector $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ and the rotation matrix \mathbf{A} —and local deformation $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_f$, as illustrated in Figure 2, that is,

$$\chi = \boldsymbol{\tau} + \mathbf{A}(\chi_0 + \bar{\mathbf{u}}_f). \quad (11)$$

FIGURE 2 | The spatial position χ of a material element of the body Ω , represented in the inertial frame \mathcal{F} , is described by a potentially large translation and rotation of the local reference frame, combined with a small deformation relative to the local frame; see Equation (11). The translation of the origin of the local frame $\bar{\mathcal{F}}$ is denoted by τ , and its orientation is described by the rotation matrix \mathbf{A} . This matrix transforms coordinates represented in the local frame—such as the reference coordinates χ_0 of an imaginary rigid configuration and the flexible displacements $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_f$ —into the inertial frame. The imaginary rigid configuration can be interpreted as the co-rotated reference configuration Ω_0 .

Note that overlined quantities $\bar{\bullet}$ are expressed in the floating frame in contrast to quantities expressed in the inertial frame \bullet .

Combining Equations (8) to (11) yields

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ [\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{I} + \nabla \bar{\mathbf{u}}_f)]^\top \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{I} + \nabla \bar{\mathbf{u}}_f) - \mathbf{I} \right\} \quad (12)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\nabla \bar{\mathbf{u}}_f + (\nabla \bar{\mathbf{u}}_f)^\top + (\nabla \bar{\mathbf{u}}_f)^\top \nabla \bar{\mathbf{u}}_f \right], \quad (13)$$

since $\tau = \tau(t)$ and due to the orthonormality of the rotation matrix, that is, $\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}$ with identity matrix \mathbf{I} .

For small deformational displacements (small strains), we neglect the nonlinear quadratic term and approximate the strain as

$$\mathbf{E} \approx \frac{1}{2} \left[\nabla \bar{\mathbf{u}}_f + (\nabla \bar{\mathbf{u}}_f)^\top \right]. \quad (14)$$

Expressing Equation (14) in Voigt notation, substituting the finite element interpolation, and omitting the approximation sign for the sake of simplicity, yields:

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{D} \mathbf{S} \bar{\mathbf{c}}_f, \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{D} is a differential operator that represents the gradients in Voigt notation. We also refer the reader to Figure 3, the discretized counterpart of Figure 2, where key variables of ACF and CRF—including the local flexible nodal displacements $\bar{\mathbf{c}}_f$ from Equation (15)—are visualized and explained in the caption.

The virtual strain variations needed in the principle of virtual work then follow from Equation (15) as

$$\delta \mathbf{e} = \mathbf{B} \frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{c}}_f}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \delta \mathbf{c}, \quad (16)$$

where the strain-displacement matrix \mathbf{B} is defined as

$$\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{D} \mathbf{S}. \quad (17)$$

Substituting these expressions into the internal virtual work integral, and using a linear elastic constitutive relation, that is, in Voigt notation,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{e} \quad (18)$$

FIGURE 3 | Finite-element-discretized domain Ω (e.g., element, substructure, or body) with global \mathcal{F} and floating $\bar{\mathcal{F}}$ frame. The translation between the frames is described by the vector τ , which represents the rigid-body translation applied identically to all finite element nodes c_i . This translation can be applied to all nodes using the projector matrix Φ , yielding $c_t = \Phi \tau$. The orientations of the frames are related by the rotation matrix A . The current position vector of node i , denoted by r_i , is composed of the reference position \bar{x}_i and the overall nodal displacement c_i , which includes: (i) the rigid body translation c_t , (ii) the rigid body rotation $c_{r_i} = (A - I)\bar{x}_i$, and (iii) the flexible deformation $c_{f_i} = A\bar{c}_{f_i}$. The deformed nodal position of node i relative to the floating frame is given by $r_{f_i} = A\bar{r}_{f_i}$, where $\bar{r}_{f_i} = \bar{c}_{f_i} + \bar{x}_i$. Note that the subscript i refers to quantities associated with a single node—when assembling all nodal quantities into a block column matrix, the subscript i is omitted. Adapted from [55].

yields

$$\int_{\Omega_0} \delta E : \Sigma dv_0 = \int_{\Omega_0} \delta e^\top \sigma dv_0 \quad (19)$$

$$= \delta c^\top \frac{\partial \bar{c}_f^\top}{\partial c} \int_{\Omega_0} \mathbf{B}^\top \mathbf{H} \mathbf{B} dv_0 \bar{c}_f \quad (20)$$

$$= \delta c^\top \frac{\partial \bar{c}_f^\top}{\partial c} \bar{\mathbf{K}} \bar{c}_f \quad (21)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{K}}$ denotes the constant stiffness matrix.

Collecting all contributions, the equations of motion take the form

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{c} + \mathbf{P}^\top \bar{\mathbf{K}} \bar{c}_f = f, \quad (22)$$

where

$$\mathbf{P} = \frac{\partial \bar{c}_f}{\partial c}. \quad (23)$$

It is important to emphasize that the principle of virtual work—and consequently the dynamic equilibrium equations—are applicable to every part of every body [56]. Therefore, Equation (22) can be used in this form both at the body level, that is, ACF, and at the finite element level, that is, CRF.

FIGURE 4 | Schematic comparison of ACF and ANCF for a beam-like structure, discretized using multiple brick elements for ACF or a single beam element for ANCF. The illustration also highlights the body-level floating frame $\bar{\mathcal{F}}$ in ACF, as well as the position vector gradients $\frac{\partial r_n}{\partial \xi_i}$ of nodes $n = 1, 2$ with the element coordinates ξ_i ($i = 1, 2, 3$) in ANCF. \mathcal{F} denotes the fixed global frame.

4 | ACF is Not the Absolute Nodal Coordinate Formulation (ANCF)

Before deriving the ACF equations of motion, it is important to clarify that ACF should not be confused with the within the multibody dynamics community more widely known ANCF. Due to their similar acronyms, readers should take care to distinguish between the two.

The key distinction between ACF and ANCF lies in their nodal degrees of freedom and deformation assumptions. ANCF elements are defined by absolute position vectors and position vector gradients as nodal coordinates [57], allowing them to model large deformations and large overall motions at the element level. In contrast, ACF employs only absolute displacements as nodal degrees of freedom and assumes small deformations at the body¹ level, as in the widely-used FFRF, which is the standard implementation for linearly-elastic flexible multibody systems [32]. For better understanding, it should be mentioned that ACF is equivalent to FFRF, the only difference being that FFRF uses rigid body coordinates and local deformation measures as degrees of freedom [32, 33]. A schematic comparison between ACF and ANCF is provided in Figure 4, highlighting the body-level floating frame for ACF and the position vector gradients for ANCF.

ANCF has been extensively studied, with reviews available in [58–60]. In contrast, ACF has received less attention but the according literature has been summarized in [32].

5 | ACF Derivation

Recalling the generic result from Section 3, we obtained

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{c}} + \mathbf{P}^\top \bar{\mathbf{K}} \bar{\mathbf{c}}_f(\mathbf{c}) = \mathbf{f}, \quad (24)$$

where it is important to emphasize that

$$\bar{\mathbf{c}}_f = \bar{\mathbf{c}}_f(\mathbf{c}), \quad (25)$$

since rigid body coordinates are absent in ACF (and CRF). Furthermore, it should be noted that ACF defines a single local frame per body, as described in detail in the introduction. This implies that Equation (24) applies at the body level, where the finite element system is assembled. In this case, $\bar{\mathbf{K}} \in \mathbb{R}^{3N \times 3N}$ (considering three degrees of freedom per node, reflecting three dimensions of space) denotes the assembled constant finite element stiffness matrix, and $\bar{\mathbf{M}} \in \mathbb{R}^{3N \times 3N}$ denotes the assembled constant finite element mass matrix from linear elastodynamics, where N refers to the number of finite element nodes. Note that the finite element mass matrix generated with displacement-based finite elements, or in

more general terms with identical shape functions used to interpolate all coordinate directions, is invariant to translations and rotations, that is, $\mathbf{M} = \overline{\mathbf{M}}$ and hence

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{A}_{bd} \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{M} \mathbf{A}_{bd} = \mathbf{A}_{bd} \mathbf{M}, \quad (26)$$

$$\overline{\mathbf{M}} = \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T \overline{\mathbf{M}} \mathbf{A}_{bd} \Leftrightarrow \overline{\mathbf{M}} \mathbf{A}_{bd} = \mathbf{A}_{bd} \overline{\mathbf{M}}, \quad (27)$$

with the block diagonal rotation matrix

$$\mathbf{A}_{bd} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{A}, \dots, \mathbf{A}), \quad (28)$$

that transforms between vectors \mathbf{v} expressed in the local (\bullet) frame and global (\bullet) frame, that is,

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{A} \overline{\mathbf{v}} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1} \Rightarrow \mathbf{c} = \mathbf{A}_{bd} \overline{\mathbf{c}} \in \mathbb{R}^{3N \times 1}, \quad (29)$$

since all finite element quantities are arranged in the standard finite element manner, that is,

$$\mathbf{c} = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 \\ \vdots \\ c_N \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{3N \times 1}. \quad (30)$$

As already mentioned (see Figure 3), multibody dynamics is often based on the decomposition of the total nodal displacement field \mathbf{c} into a rigid body translation \mathbf{c}_t , rigid body rotation \mathbf{c}_r , and deformation \mathbf{c}_f , that is,

$$\mathbf{c} = \mathbf{c}_t + \mathbf{c}_r + \mathbf{c}_f. \quad (31)$$

In Equation (24) we have to express $\overline{\mathbf{c}}_f$ in terms \mathbf{c} , which can be achieved with the help of Equation (29) and Equation (31). Hence,

$$\overline{\mathbf{c}}_f = \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{rb}), \quad (32)$$

with the rigid body motion

$$\mathbf{c}_{rb}(\mathbf{c}) = \mathbf{c}_t(\mathbf{c}) + \mathbf{c}_r(\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{c})), \quad (33)$$

and

$$\mathbf{A}_{bd} = \mathbf{A}_{bd}(\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{c})), \quad (34)$$

since no rotation parameters are used as generalized coordinates in the ACF. However, there are several possibilities to obtain the rigid body motion from the global nodal displacements as discussed in the introduction. Based on Equation (32), we can derive the projector matrix \mathbf{P} via its definition stated in Equation (23),² which gives

$$\mathbf{P} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T}{\partial \mathbf{c}} (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{rb}) + \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T \left(\mathbf{I}_{bd} - \frac{\partial \mathbf{c}_{rb}}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \right). \quad (36)$$

Note that the virtual elastic work done by rigid body displacements is zero—rigid body displacements cannot give rise to internal forces, that is,

$$\mathbf{c}_f^T \mathbf{A}_{bd} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T \delta \mathbf{c}_{rb} = \mathbf{c}_f^T \mathbf{A}_{bd} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{c}_{rb}}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \delta \mathbf{c} = 0, \quad (37)$$

which must hold for any virtual displacement, and, therefore, implies that (given $\overline{\mathbf{K}} = \overline{\mathbf{K}}^T$)

$$\mathbf{c}_f^T \mathbf{A}_{bd} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{c}_{rb}}{\partial \mathbf{c}} = \mathbf{0} \quad \overset{\text{transpose}}{\Leftrightarrow} \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{c}_{rb}}{\partial \mathbf{c}^T} \mathbf{A}_{bd} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T \mathbf{c}_f = \mathbf{0}, \quad (38)$$

which means there is no need to take the last term in Equation (36) in the equations of motion into account. Hence, we find [19, 33]

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{c}} + \mathbf{A}_{bd} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{rb}) + (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{rb})^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}_{bd}}{\partial \mathbf{c}^T} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{rb}) = \mathbf{f}, \quad (39)$$

and the evaluation of the derivative of the rotation matrix with respect to the nodal displacements depends on the method used to obtain the rigid body rotation from the global displacement field, as already discussed. Equation (39) represents the form of the equations of motion of the ACF known from literature.

The ACF equations of motion can be solved efficiently even with an implicit time integration scheme due to a constant co-rotated Jacobian employed in quasi Newton's method, that is, [19]

$$J^{-1} \approx \mathbf{A}_{bd} \left(\underbrace{\mathbf{M} + \frac{h^2}{4} \overline{\mathbf{K}}}_{\text{const. if } h=\text{const.}} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{A}_{bd}^T, \quad (40)$$

with step size h .

6 | CRF Derivation

In contrast to ACF, CRF does not use one local frame per body, but one frame per element (e). Therefore the frame of each element follows its gross motion [3, tab. 1, p. 555]. The commonly used EICR [14, p. 3] is derived via the procedure laid out in [14, section 2.1, pp. 3–6] for continuum finite elements. The possible additional rotational generalized coordinates of structural elements are not discussed in this paper.

Transferring the generic result from Section 3 to this case, we have

$$\mathbf{M}^{(e)} \ddot{\mathbf{c}}^{(e)} + \mathbf{f}_{el,EICR}^{(e)} = \mathbf{f}^{(e)}. \quad (41)$$

where the EICR internal force vector is given by

$$\mathbf{f}_{el,EICR}^{(e)} = \left(\frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{c}}_f^{(e)}}{\partial \mathbf{c}^{(e)}} \right)^T \overline{\mathbf{K}}^{(e)} \overline{\mathbf{c}}_f^{(e)}. \quad (42)$$

The local deformational displacement is then written as (see Figure 3)

$$\overline{\mathbf{c}}_f^{(e)} = \mathbf{A}_{bd}^{(e)T} \mathbf{r}^{(e)} - \overline{\mathbf{x}}^{(e)}, \quad (43)$$

with the global nodal positions $\mathbf{r}^{(e)} = \mathbf{c}^{(e)} + \overline{\mathbf{x}}^{(e)}$ and constant reference positions $\overline{\mathbf{x}}^{(e)}$ of element (e), where the rigid body translation can be removed, because it does not contribute to the elastic forces, hence, the derivation focuses only on the influence of the element's rigid body rotation on the analysis [14, section 2.1, pp. 3–6].

With Equation (43) the derivative in Equation (42) yields

$$\frac{\partial \overline{\mathbf{c}}_f^{(e)}}{\partial \mathbf{c}^{(e)}} = \mathbf{A}_{bd}^{(e)T} + \left. \frac{\partial \left(\mathbf{A}_{bd}^{(e)T} \mathbf{r}^{(e)} \right)}{\partial \mathbf{c}^{(e)}} \right|_{\mathbf{r}^{(e)}=\text{const.}} \quad (44)$$

The first term is the rotation matrix of the element. The second part is conventionally written as³

$$\left. \frac{\partial \left(\mathbf{A}_{bd}^{(e)T} \mathbf{r}^{(e)} \right)}{\partial \mathbf{c}^{(e)}} \right|_{\mathbf{r}^{(e)}=\text{const.}} = -\overline{\mathbf{S}}^{(e)} \overline{\mathbf{G}}_{\overline{\mathbf{c}}}^{(e)} \mathbf{A}_{bd}^{(e)T}, \quad (45)$$

where

$$\overline{\mathbf{S}}_{\overline{\mathbf{r}}}^{(e)} = \left[\overline{\mathbf{r}}_1^{(e)} \ \cdots \ \overline{\mathbf{r}}_N^{(e)} \right]^T, \quad (46)$$

is the local spin-lever or moment arm matrix using the tilde operator

$$\mathbf{v} = \begin{bmatrix} v_x \\ v_y \\ v_z \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \tilde{\mathbf{v}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -v_z & v_y \\ v_z & 0 & -v_x \\ -v_y & v_x & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (47)$$

The matrix $\overline{\mathbf{G}}_{\bar{c}}^{(e)}$ is called the spin-fitter matrix, which links the element's instantaneous infinitesimal spin pseudo vector $\partial\overline{\boldsymbol{\psi}}^{(e)} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}$ to the change of the local nodal displacements, that is,

$$\overline{\mathbf{G}}_{\bar{c}}^{(e)} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial\overline{\boldsymbol{\psi}}^{(e)}}{\partial\bar{c}_1^{(e)}} & \dots & \frac{\partial\overline{\boldsymbol{\psi}}^{(e)}}{\partial\bar{c}_N^{(e)}} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3N}. \quad (48)$$

How the spin-fitter matrix is comprised in detail depends on the finite element type and on the way the element local frame is constructed from the global displacements, see [27]. In general this relation is nonlinear. Another derivative of this term is needed to obtain the consistent tangent stiffness matrix, but is neglected in many existing works due to the complexity. For some cases as with highly warped shell elements in a coarse mesh this simplification may not be appropriate [14, p. 5].

Hence, [14, section 2.1, pp. 3–6]

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{ela,EICR}}^{(e)} = \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^{(e)} \left(\mathbf{I}_{\text{bd}}^{(e)} - \overline{\mathbf{S}}_{\bar{r}}^{(e)} \overline{\mathbf{G}}_{\bar{c}}^{(e)} \right)^{\top} \overline{\mathbf{K}}^{(e)} \bar{\mathbf{c}}_{\text{f}}^{(e)}, \quad (49)$$

where the term in brackets,

$$\overline{\mathbf{P}}^{(e)} = \mathbf{I}_{\text{bd}}^{(e)} - \overline{\mathbf{S}}_{\bar{r}}^{(e)} \overline{\mathbf{G}}_{\bar{c}}^{(e)}, \quad (50)$$

represents the local projector matrix [14, p. 5]. Therefore,

$$\mathbf{M}^{(e)} \bar{\mathbf{c}}^{(e)} + \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^{(e)} \left(\mathbf{I}_{\text{bd}}^{(e)} - \overline{\mathbf{S}}_{\bar{r}}^{(e)} \overline{\mathbf{G}}_{\bar{c}}^{(e)} \right)^{\top} \overline{\mathbf{K}}^{(e)} \bar{\mathbf{c}}_{\text{f}}^{(e)} = \mathbf{f}^{(e)}, \quad (51)$$

where \mathbf{I}_{bd} represents an identity matrix of appropriate size.

7 | Comparison of ACF and CRF

Comparing the starting points of the derivations in Section 5 and Section 6, it becomes apparent that both formulations are based on the same generic form of the equations of motion (see Section 3) and the same coordinates, that is, \mathbf{c} . The distinction lies in the level of definition: while ACF defines the involved quantities at the body level, CRF defines them on an element-by-element basis. That is, ACF employs a single floating frame for the entire body, whereas CRF uses a separate floating frame for each element. In other words, ACF assumes the same reference motion for all elements, while CRF allows for individual reference motion for each element. If the same number of reference frames and the same rotation-matrix construction are used, the two equations of motion are identical. Note that, if reference frames are chosen at different levels (element, substructure, or body), computational results will differ; the extent of this difference depends on the specific problem and may warrant future investigation. Also, due to the differing levels of definition, in CRF the elastic forces must be assembled at each iteration, whereas ACF can directly use the pre-assembled stiffness matrix.

As outlined in Section 2, we have clarified the assumptions underlying the comparison between ACF and CRF. Specifically, we consider displacement-based finite elements with a constant and rotation-invariant mass matrix. Under these conditions, the inertia forces take the simple linear form shown in Equation (39) and Equation (51), which corresponds to standard linear elastodynamics. Therefore, after assembly, the mass matrices in ACF and CRF are identical. Consequently, within this framework, the inertia forces are also identical, since both ACF and CRF use the same coordinates, that is, \mathbf{c} .

Nevertheless, at first glance, the elastic forces appear different, whether using the ACF elastic forces at the element level or the CRF elastic forces at the body level, that is,

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{el,ACF}} = \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^{\top} (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{\text{rb}}) + (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{\text{rb}})^{\top} \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}}{\partial \mathbf{c}^{\top}} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^{\top} (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{\text{rb}}), \quad (52)$$

versus

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{el,EICR}} = \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}} \left(\mathbf{I}_{\text{bd}} - \overline{\mathbf{S}}_r \overline{\mathbf{G}}_c \right)^\top \overline{\mathbf{K}} \overline{\mathbf{c}}_f, \quad (53)$$

where the element superscripts have been omitted for clarity and ease of comparison.

Starting the comparison, we clearly see that

$$\mathbf{c}_f = \mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{\text{rb}}, \quad (54)$$

and

$$\mathbf{c}_f = \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}} \overline{\mathbf{c}}_f, \quad (55)$$

$$\overline{\mathbf{c}}_f = \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top \mathbf{c}_f. \quad (56)$$

Hence,

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{el,ACF}} = \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \overline{\mathbf{c}}_f + \mathbf{c}_f^\top \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}}{\partial \mathbf{c}^\top} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \overline{\mathbf{c}}_f, \quad (57)$$

which proves that the first term in Equation (52) equals the first one in Equation (53).

The second term warrants closer examination and necessitates some preliminary developments: The rotation matrix is an orthonormal matrix, that is,

$$\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}, \quad (58)$$

which after differentiation with respect to time implies

$$\dot{\overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}} = \mathbf{A}^\top \dot{\mathbf{A}} \Leftrightarrow \dot{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{A} \dot{\overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}}, \quad (59)$$

with local angular velocity

$$\overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} = \begin{bmatrix} \overline{\omega}_x \\ \overline{\omega}_y \\ \overline{\omega}_z \end{bmatrix} \Leftrightarrow \dot{\overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\overline{\omega}_z & \overline{\omega}_y \\ \overline{\omega}_z & 0 & -\overline{\omega}_x \\ -\overline{\omega}_y & \overline{\omega}_x & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (60)$$

Also

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}(t)), \quad (61)$$

with rotation parametrization $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, and therefore by the chain rule of differentiation

$$\dot{\mathbf{A}} = \sum_i \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \theta_i} \dot{\theta}_i. \quad (62)$$

Combining Equation (59) and Equation (62) yields

$$\dot{\overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}} = \sum_i \mathbf{A}^\top \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \theta_i} \dot{\theta}_i \Leftrightarrow \overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}} = \sum_i \text{axial} \left(\mathbf{A}^\top \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \theta_i} \right) \dot{\theta}_i \quad (63)$$

$$= \overline{\mathbf{G}}_\theta \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \quad (64)$$

where $\mathbf{A}^\top \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \theta_i}$ is also skew-symmetric and $\text{axial} \left(\mathbf{A}^\top \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial \theta_i} \right)$ is the i^{th} column of $\overline{\mathbf{G}}_\theta = \overline{\mathbf{G}}_\theta(\boldsymbol{\theta})$. Note that $\mathbf{v} = \text{axial}(\dot{\mathbf{v}})$. Hence, from Equation (63) it can be inferred that

$$\overline{\mathbf{G}}_\theta = \frac{\partial \overline{\boldsymbol{\omega}}}{\partial \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}} \quad (65)$$

$$= \frac{\partial \overline{\boldsymbol{\psi}}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}, \quad (66)$$

where the ‘‘cancel the dot’’ rule has been used to obtain Equation (66).

With these preparations in mind, let us consider now the derivative of the rotation matrix in Equation (52), which may be written as

$$\mathbf{c}_f^\top \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}_{bd}}{\partial \mathbf{c}^\top} = \left(\frac{\partial (\mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top \mathbf{c}_f)}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \Big|_{\mathbf{c}_f = \text{const.}} \right)^\top. \quad (67)$$

Since $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}(\mathbf{c}))$, we have

$$\frac{\partial (\mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top \mathbf{c}_f)}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \Big|_{\mathbf{c}_f = \text{const.}} = \frac{\partial (\mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top \mathbf{c}_f)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \Big|_{\mathbf{c}_f = \text{const.}} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}{\partial \mathbf{c}}, \quad (68)$$

where

$$\frac{\partial (\mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top \mathbf{c}_f)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \Big|_{\mathbf{c}_f = \text{const.}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial (\mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top \mathbf{c}_{f_1})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \Big|_{\mathbf{c}_{f_1} = \text{const.}} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial (\mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top \mathbf{c}_{f_N})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \Big|_{\mathbf{c}_{f_N} = \text{const.}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (69)$$

Furthermore, for any vector \mathbf{v} using the “cancel the dot” rule, we have

$$\frac{\partial (\mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{v})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \Big|_{\mathbf{v} = \text{const.}} = \frac{\partial (\dot{\mathbf{A}}^\top \mathbf{v})}{\partial \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}} \Big|_{\mathbf{v} = \text{const.}} = \tilde{\mathbf{v}} \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_\theta, \quad (70)$$

since

$$\dot{\mathbf{A}}^\top \mathbf{v} = (\dot{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\omega}})^\top \mathbf{v} \quad (71)$$

$$= \tilde{\boldsymbol{\omega}}^\top \mathbf{A}^\top \mathbf{v} \quad (72)$$

$$= -\tilde{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \mathbf{v} \quad (73)$$

$$= \tilde{\mathbf{v}} \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_\theta \dot{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \quad (74)$$

which can be applied to the nodal structure of Equation (69), that is,

$$\frac{\partial (\mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top \mathbf{c}_f)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \Big|_{\mathbf{c}_f = \text{const.}} = \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_f \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_\theta, \quad (75)$$

where

$$\tilde{\mathbf{c}}_f = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_{f_1} \\ \vdots \\ \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_{f_N} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{3N \times 3}. \quad (76)$$

Finally,

$$\frac{\partial (\mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top \mathbf{c}_f)}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \Big|_{\mathbf{c}_f = \text{const.}} = \frac{\partial (\mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top \mathbf{c}_f)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \Big|_{\mathbf{c}_f = \text{const.}} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \quad (77)$$

$$= \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_f \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_\theta \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}{\partial \bar{\mathbf{c}}} \frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{c}}}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \quad (78)$$

$$= \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_f \frac{\partial \bar{\boldsymbol{\psi}}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}{\partial \bar{\mathbf{c}}} \frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{c}}}{\partial \mathbf{c}} \quad (79)$$

$$= \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_f \tilde{\mathbf{G}}_{\bar{\mathbf{c}}} \mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top, \quad (80)$$

since

$$\bar{\mathbf{c}} = \mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top \mathbf{c} \Rightarrow \frac{\partial \bar{\mathbf{c}}}{\partial \mathbf{c}} = \mathbf{A}_{bd}^\top, \quad (81)$$

and where

$$\bar{\mathbf{G}}_{\bar{\mathbf{c}}} = \frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}{\partial \bar{\mathbf{c}}} \quad (82)$$

$$= \frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial \bar{\mathbf{c}}}, \quad (83)$$

which is equal to Equation (48). Hence,

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{el,ACF}} = \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}} \left(\mathbf{I}_{\text{bd}} + \tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_f \bar{\mathbf{G}}_{\bar{\mathbf{c}}} \right)^\top \bar{\mathbf{K}} \bar{\mathbf{c}}_f, \quad (84)$$

where two differences compared to Equation (53) remain — the sign and different spin-lever matrix in the second term in the elastic force expression. The sign is easily explained by the fact that the spin-lever matrix is the negative nodal tilde matrix, that is,

$$\bar{\mathbf{S}}_{\tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_f} = \left[\tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_{f_1} \cdots \tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_{f_N} \right]^\top \quad (85)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_{f_1}^\top \\ \vdots \\ \tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_{f_N}^\top \end{bmatrix} \quad (86)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} -\tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_{f_1} \\ \vdots \\ -\tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_{f_N} \end{bmatrix} \quad (87)$$

$$= -\tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_f. \quad (88)$$

The remaining difference between Equations (49) and (84) is the use of $\tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{r}}}$ or $\tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_f$ respectively. To explain this let us express the current position of the nodes as [33, p. 249] (see also Figure 3)

$$\mathbf{r} = \boldsymbol{\Phi} \boldsymbol{\tau} + \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}} (\bar{\mathbf{x}} + \bar{\mathbf{c}}_f), \quad (89)$$

where the rigid body translation modes,

$$\boldsymbol{\Phi} = [\mathbf{I} \cdots \mathbf{I}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{3N \times 3}, \quad (90)$$

apply the rigid body translation $\boldsymbol{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}$ of the floating frame to all finite element nodes. Hence,

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}} = \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top \mathbf{r} \quad (91)$$

$$= \boldsymbol{\Phi} \bar{\boldsymbol{\tau}} + \bar{\mathbf{x}} + \bar{\mathbf{c}}_f \quad (92)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\boldsymbol{\tau}} \\ \vdots \\ \bar{\boldsymbol{\tau}} \end{bmatrix} + \bar{\mathbf{x}} + \bar{\mathbf{c}}_f, \quad (93)$$

since

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top \boldsymbol{\Phi} = \boldsymbol{\Phi} \mathbf{A}^\top. \quad (94)$$

Hence,

$$\tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{r}}} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}} \\ \vdots \\ \tilde{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}} \end{bmatrix} + \tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}} + \tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_f \quad (95)$$

$$= \boldsymbol{\Phi} \tilde{\tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}} + \tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{x}}} + \tilde{\tilde{\mathbf{c}}}_f, \quad (96)$$

which is multiplied with the finite element stiffness matrix. Since $\tilde{\bar{\mathbf{x}}}$ and Φ are the rigid body rotation and translation modes, respectively,

$$(\Phi \tilde{\bar{\mathbf{r}}} + \tilde{\bar{\mathbf{x}}})^\top \bar{\mathbf{K}} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (97)$$

since rigid body modes lie in the null space of the stiffness matrix, and hence

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}} \left(\mathbf{I}_{\text{bd}} + \tilde{\bar{\mathbf{c}}}_f \bar{\mathbf{G}}_c \right)^\top \bar{\mathbf{K}} \bar{\mathbf{c}}_f = \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}} \left(\mathbf{I}_{\text{bd}} + \tilde{\bar{\mathbf{r}}} \bar{\mathbf{G}}_c \right)^\top \bar{\mathbf{K}} \bar{\mathbf{c}}_f, \quad (98)$$

which proves that

$$\mathbf{f}_{\text{el,ACF}} = \mathbf{f}_{\text{el,EICR}}. \quad (99)$$

The equations of motion can be implemented in either form, that is, Equation (52) or Equation (53); in any case the rotation matrix \mathbf{A} needs to be constructed from the total global displacement field \mathbf{c} . With it the local flexible displacement can be calculated as (see also Figure 3)

$$\bar{\mathbf{c}}_f = \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top \mathbf{c}_f \quad (100)$$

$$= \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{\text{rb}}) \quad (101)$$

$$= \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_t - \mathbf{c}_r) \quad (102)$$

$$= \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top \left(\mathbf{c} - \frac{1}{N} \Phi \Phi^\top \mathbf{c} - (\mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}} \bar{\mathbf{x}} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}) \right) \quad (103)$$

$$= \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top \left(\mathbf{c} - \frac{1}{N} \Phi \Phi^\top \mathbf{c} + \bar{\mathbf{x}} \right) - \bar{\mathbf{x}}. \quad (104)$$

Since the extractor matrix

$$\frac{1}{N} \Phi \Phi^\top = \frac{1}{N} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} & \cdots & \mathbf{I} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{I} & \cdots & \mathbf{I} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{3N \times 3N} \quad (105)$$

of the rigid body translation,

$$\mathbf{c}_t = \frac{1}{N} \Phi \Phi^\top \mathbf{c}, \quad (106)$$

calculated as the average nodal displacements, commutes with the block diagonal rotation matrix, that is,

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top \Phi \Phi^\top = \Phi \Phi^\top \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top, \quad (107)$$

the rigid body translation term in Equation (104) can be omitted since

$$\bar{\mathbf{K}} \Phi = \mathbf{0}, \quad (108)$$

that is, Φ is part of the null space of the stiffness matrix $\bar{\mathbf{K}}$. Note that the projector matrix used in Equation (105) is just one of several possible approaches to extract the rigid body translation from the overall nodal displacements; see the discussion in Section 1.

In both formulations there is always one reference frame per certain unit (body or element). However, sometimes one would need more frames per body but not one per each element because it is computationally too costly. Such a practical requirement motivates the approach, where there will be one frame per substructure (group of elements within a body). The substructures can be directly assembled in the standard finite element manner due to the use of absolute nodal coordinates, eliminating the need for Lagrange multipliers.

8 | Conclusions

In conclusion, this paper establishes the equivalence between the corotational finite element formulation (CRF) from the finite element community, that is,

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{c}} + \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}} \left(\mathbf{I}_{\text{bd}} - \overline{\mathbf{S}}_r \overline{\mathbf{G}}_c \right)^\top \overline{\mathbf{K}} \overline{\mathbf{c}}_f = \mathbf{f},$$

and absolute coordinate formulation (ACF) from the multibody dynamics community, that is,

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{c}} + \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{\text{rb}}) + (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{\text{rb}})^\top \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}}{\partial \mathbf{c}^\top} \overline{\mathbf{K}} \mathbf{A}_{\text{bd}}^\top (\mathbf{c} - \mathbf{c}_{\text{rb}}) = \mathbf{f},$$

demonstrating that the only distinction lies in the number of local reference frames used—element-based in CRF and body-based in ACF.

Additionally, the paper discusses the computational challenges associated with the CRF in real-world multibody dynamics simulations, where partitioning bodies into substructures, each with its own local reference frame, can help alleviate these difficulties. The substructures can then be assembled in the standard finite element manner, since absolute nodal coordinates are employed in ACF/CRF.

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Data Availability Statement

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

Endnotes

¹As demonstrated in this paper, ACF can also be applied per substructure or per element, with the latter being equivalent to CRF, as also shown.

²Note that in general,

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{T}}{\partial \mathbf{u}} \mathbf{v} = \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{T}}{\partial u_1} \mathbf{v} \quad \dots \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{T}}{\partial u_n} \mathbf{v} \right]. \quad (35)$$

³The derivation of Equation (45) is explained in detail in Section 7, where a comprehensive comparison between ACF and CRF is provided. The reader is especially referred to Equation (67), as well as the preceding and subsequent equations, for full context and clarification. This section is intended primarily to present the final form of the CRF elastic forces and to highlight that, at first glance, they may appear different from those in ACF. To avoid redundancy, the more detailed derivation is provided only once in the referenced section.

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